

Multicomponent Phosphorescence Spectrum of Triphenylamine and its Separation by MIDP Spectroscopy[†]

T. N. MISRA

Optics Department, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-700 032

and

NORIKO IWASAKI and MINORU KINOSHITA

The Institute for Solid State Physics, The University of Tokyo, Roppongi, Minato-ku, Tokyo 106, Japan

The phosphorescence spectra of triphenylamine have been measured in various matrices at 1.4 K. In the neat crystal, the O,O band is most intense, while in the other matrices, the bands around at $0-100\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is assigned to the movement of the ensemble of three benzene rings, appear very strongly. The dependence of the spectra on matrices is interpreted by difference in molecular conformation.

INTEREST in the study of aromatic amines stems from the fact that the phosphorescence to the fluorescence quantum yield ratio is large and the mean phosphorescence life time is short in these molecules compared to those in aromatic hydrocarbons. This enhancement of spin-orbit coupling in aromatic amines is very sensitive to the twisting of the lone-pair orbital (*l*-orbital) axis of the nitrogen atom relative to the attached ring planes^{1,2}. In addition to this fact, in aromatic amines which have more than two benzene rings, the interaction between rings plays an important role in the optical properties. The MO calculations have shown that the electron-transfer interaction between the two benzene rings of diphenylamine³ is important in interpreting the absorption spectrum of the molecule. Due to these facts we can expect the radiative properties of aromatic amines depend very much on the molecular geometry and therefore, on matrices.

In this paper we report the phosphorescence spectra of triphenylamine in a neat crystal and in some other matrices at liquid helium temperature. In the neat crystal, the phosphorescence spectrum is very sharp, while in other matrices, it is very broad and is separated into the spectra of several components with the aid of MIDP (microwave induced delayed phosphorescence) spectroscopy. The dependence of spectra on matrices is interpreted by difference in molecular geometry.

Experimental

Triphenylamine (Tokyo Kasei Co.) was purified by recrystallisation from ethanol, vacuum sublimation and finally by zone-refining (more than 100 passes). The substances used as matrices were purified by the same procedure. Neat and mixed crystals were grown by Bridgman method.

The samples were excited by an Ushio 250 W high pressure Hg lamp through Toshiba UV-D33S filter. An 8 bits, 64 kbytes microcomputer 20 IF800 (Oki Denki Co., Ltd.) controlled the experimental equipment consisting of excitation and detection shutters, microwave sweep oscillators (Hewlett Packard 8620A and Weinsell 221), a Jobin-Yvon HR1000 monochromator and a Biomation 805 waveform recorder. Simultaneously the microcomputer treated the signals from the waveform recorder by appropriate procedure and accumulated the data.

The MIDP spectroscopy was applied for separating a multicomponent emission into a set of spectra of individual components. This method was originally used for obtaining a set of sub-level spectra⁴. However, the method utilising a lock-in amplifier is sometimes subject to difficulty in determining a uniform baseline over a whole spectral region. Especially, the difficulty arises when it is applied to multicomponent emission and strongly emitting components do not respond to the applied microwaves resonant to a particular component. The use of a microcomputer makes it possible to compensate the background even in such a case. A CRT display of the initial setting for taking an MIDP spectrum is shown in Fig. 1. The phosphorescence decay curves with and without microwaves are alternately measured at a certain wavelength and shown here as a superposition. In this particular example, two zero-field microwave transitions are observed; one is weak at 2.19 GHz and the other is strong at 2.25 GHz. The vertical lines are input from the computer console to separate the regions of the dark level and the transitions. The dark level in the region I is used commonly to correct the intensity in the regions II and III.

The integrated intensity of the MIDP signal in the region II, for instance, at the wavelength

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

A part of the article was presented at the National Conference on Spectroscopy and Theoretical Chemistry held at Calcutta, December 5-7, 1985.

Fig. 1. A hard copy of the CRT display showing the initial setting for obtaining MIDP spectra. There are two MIDP signals which are separated by the vertical lines as the regions II and III. The region I determines the dark level. The microwave transitions occur at 2.19 and 2.25 GHz. The output of ramp voltage for microwave sweep is indicated by an inset denoted by MW.

λ , $I_{II,\lambda}$, is given by

$$I_{II,\lambda} = \sum_{t_i} \{I_M(t_i) - I_0(t_i)\}_\lambda, \quad (\text{region II})$$

where, $I_M(t_i)$ and $I_0(t_i)$ are the intensity of the decay with and without microwaves at time t_i , respectively. The summation runs over the whole time

region of II. For a weak signal, the intensity data may be accumulated to improve S/N ratio, and then the spectrometer is scanned to the next wavelength successively. In this way, the MIDP spectrum of the component responding to the microwaves of 2.19 GHz is obtained. The spectrum for the species resonant to the microwaves of 2.25 GHz corresponding to the region III is also stored simultaneously in the computer. The MIDP spectra shown in Fig. 5 were obtained in this way.

Results

Neat crystal: The phosphorescence spectrum of the triphenylamine neat crystal at 1.4 K is shown in Fig. 2. The lower spectrum was measured with 10 μm entrance and exit slit widths and the upper one was recorded with 70 μm slit widths in order to magnify relatively weak vibrational band structure. The O, O band is very strong and very sharp. Only one species seems to contribute to the phosphorescence in the neat crystal. Indeed, no emission from any other traps is observed even when the temperature is elevated to 4.2 K.

Several weak but sharp vibrational bands are observed at 0-100, 0-288, 0-718 and 0-1 593 cm^{-1} . The assignments of the vibrational bands in the spectrum have been performed on the basis of the vibrational analysis of ir and Raman spectra of related aromatic amines⁶ and on referring to a few ir and Raman data previously reported for tri-

Fig. 2 The phosphorescence spectrum of the triphenylamine neat crystal at 1.4 K. The upper trace is a magnification with wider slit widths.

Fig. 3. The phosphorescence spectrum of triphenylamine in diphenylamine at 1.4 K.

phenylamine^{6,7}. The band at $0-100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the ensemble movement of the three benzene rings. The band at $0-288\text{ cm}^{-1}$ would be due to the C-N-C deformation. The band at $0-718\text{ cm}^{-1}$ would be assigned to the vibrational mode of benzene rings of which the frequency changes very much with substituents attached to N in aromatic amines. These vibrations which are related to the nitrogen atom appear relatively strongly among the vibronic bands observed in the phosphorescence spectrum. On the other hand, the following vibrations which are mainly distributed on the benzene moiety appear very weak. These vibrations are 418 , 754 , 998 and $1\ 169\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and are assigned to the vibrations originating from ν_{16} , ν_{11} , ν_1 and ν_6 of benzene, respectively. Only the band at $0-1\ 593\text{ cm}^{-1}$ also originating from benzene ν_6 appears relatively strongly.

The phosphorescence decay of the triphenylamine neat crystal is exponential even at 1.4 K with the lifetime of 270 ms. The spin-lattice relaxation is not suppressed and no microwave transitions are observed in the neat crystal.

In diphenylamine: The phosphorescence spectrum of triphenylamine in diphenylamine is shown in Fig. 3. The spectrum becomes very broad, but there are some very weak vibrational bands superimposed on it. The vibrational analysis of these bands indicates the presence of at least two emitting species as denoted by *a* and *b* in the spectrum in addition to the species giving rise to the broad spectrum. The vibrational frequencies of the bands correspond

well to those observed in the neat crystal. The MIDP signals are observed around 2.24 and 1.96 GHz. A similar spectrum of triphenylamine is also observed in the bis(4-bromophenyl) ether host.

In methylcyclohexane (MCH): The phosphorescence spectrum of triphenylamine in MCH shows somewhat complicated behaviour. The spectra partly shown in Fig. 4 indicate that there is a concentration dependence. At a concentration higher than $10^{-4}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ the spectrum shows the maximum at 407.5 nm. When the concentration is lower than $10^{-5}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ the maximum position shifts to 409.5 nm and the very sharp band appears at 405.6 nm.

The MIDP signals are observed at 2.19, 2.25, 2.31 and 2.33 GHz. The decay rate constants for the fast decaying components are commonly found to be about 4.5 s^{-1} and those for the slowly decaying components about 0.5 s^{-1} . The relative intensities of these signals also show a concentration dependence. The signals are very weak at $10^{-8}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. At $10^{-4}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the signals at 2.25, 2.31 and 2.33 GHz are strong, but the signal at 2.19 GHz is weak. At $10^{-6}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, on the contrary, the signal at 2.19 GHz is strong, but the others become weak.

To see the relation between the phosphorescence spectrum and the microwave transitions, the MIDP spectra are measured around the O,O band at 1.4 K. The emission spectra from the components, those responded to the microwaves of 2.33, 2.31, 2.25 and 2.19 GHz, are shown in Fig. 5. The MIDP spectra

Fig. 4. The phosphorescence spectra of triphenylamine in methylocyclohexane at various concentrations and at 1.4 K.

observed at 2.33, 2.31 and 2.25 GHz are shifted from each other, but the spectral shapes are almost identical with each other having a shoulder band separated by about 110 cm^{-1} from the main peak. This wavenumber corresponds well to the vibration assigned to the ensemble motion of the phenyl groups. Thus, these three spectra could be ascribed to triphenylamine embedded in different environments in MCH.

The MIDP spectrum obtained at 2.19 GHz, is broad in comparison with the others and seems to consist of several components. This might mean that the signal at 2.19 GHz includes the counterparts of the other signals originally belonging to degenerate transitions and consists of three or more components. We have tried EEDOR (electron-electron double resonance) experiments to find any correlation among these signals, but without any success. We have also tried to further decompose the MIDP signal at 2.19 GHz into any components by narrowing the sweep width of the microwaves, but have not succeeded in obtaining any definite result. From

these observations, it seems to be probable that the four signals belong to different species of triphenylamine.

Fig. 5. The MIDP spectra of triphenylamine in methylocyclohexane ($10^{-4}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) around the O,O band at 1.4 K. The multicomponent emission is separated into four components by the microwave transitions at the frequencies indicated.

Discussion

The phosphorescence spectrum of triphenylamine changes markedly depending on matrices. This finding is just in accordance with the expectation we made in the introductory section. As the spin-orbit coupling in aromatic amines is dependent on the relative orientation of the *l*-orbital and the benzene ring planes, the radiative properties of triphenylamine would be sensitively determined by the twist angle of phenyl groups to a pyramidal plane and the C-N-C angle.

These angles are expected to be susceptible to the environmental effect and the molecular conformation would be determined by the environment of the molecule embedded. In the gas phase, the

electron diffraction studies⁹ have shown that triphenylamine has the C_3 symmetry and the twist angle and the C-N-C angle are 47 ± 5 and 116° , respectively. In a benzene solution, the C-N-C angle has been estimated to be $110-107^\circ$ from the measurements of electric dipole moment¹⁰. On the other hand, the analysis of the crystal structure of triphenylamine has not yet been completed; it has been terminated at the stage that there are either two or four molecules in the asymmetric unit¹¹. However, the molecular structure in a crystal may be inferred from the structure of triphenylphosphin. In a crystal, triphenylphosphin has no C_3 symmetry and the angles of three benzene ring planes relative to the pyramidal planes are not equal¹². This is explained by the repulsion due to inter-molecular forces rather than the repulsion of the hydrogen atoms within the molecule. Probably this result would also apply to triphenylamine and this susceptibility to the environmental effect on molecular conformation would explain the difference observed in the phosphorescence spectra of this compound.

In the neat crystal, most of the phosphorescence intensity is concentrated on the well-defined O,O band and the vibrations mainly associated with the benzene rings carry the intensity only slightly. This suggests that the density of the two unpaired electrons comprising the triplet state is comparatively high in the proximity of the central nitrogen atom, although the results of photoelectron spectroscopy⁸ indicate that the highest occupied molecular orbital of triphenylamine is the π -orbital which is spread over the benzene rings. In MCH, on the other hand, the vibronic bands at 0-110 and around 0-1 500 cm^{-1} which are related to the vibrations in the benzene moiety become very strong, indicating that the two electrons have higher probability to reside on the benzene rings. Therefore, in the neat crystal, triphenylamine seems to take a conformation favorable for admixture of the (I, π^*) state into the lowest triplet state, whereas in MCH it takes conformations less favorable for admixture. Since it is the (I, π^*)

state that is most responsible for the spin-orbit coupling, even a slight change in the degree of its admixture would have rather large effect on the radiative properties of such a molecule as triphenylamine which is liable to the environmental perturbations. In other words, the phosphorescence spectrum of triphenylamine is subject to a marked change depending on matrices, even though the molecular conformations in different matrices are varying only slightly from each other.

In methylcyclohexane, the spectra show the concentration dependence. The reason for this is not clear at this stage. There may exist molecular aggregates at higher concentration, or there may also be a possibility that methylcyclohexane takes different structures depending on the concentration of triphenylamine.

References

1. M. KASHA and H. R. RAWLS, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1968, **7**, 561.
2. E. C. LIM and M. KEDZERSKI, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1973, **20**, 242.
3. T. HINOHARA, S. CHO and T. MORITA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **44**, 629.
4. E. KANEZAKI, N. NISHI, M. KINOSHITA and K. NIIMORI, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1974, **29**, 529.
5. A. FERRIER-DATIN and J.-M. LEBAS, *J. Chem. Physicochim. Biol.*, 1972, **69**, 591.
6. R. T. O. BROWNLEE, R. E. J. HUTCHINSON, A. R. KATRITZKY, T. T. TIDWELL and R. D. TOPSOM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1757.
7. S. HIGUCHI, H. TSUYAMA, S. TANAKA and H. KAMADA, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1973, **30**, 463.
8. T. P. DEBIES and J. W. RABALAIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 308.
9. Y. SASAKI, K. KIMURA and M. KUBO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, **31**, 477.
10. O. W. N. CUMPER and A. P. THURSTON, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1971, 422.
11. E. R. HOWELLS, F. M. LOVELL, D. ROGERS and A. J. C. WILSON, *Acta Cryst.*, 1954, **7**, 298.
12. J. J. DALY, *Z. Krist.*, 1963, **118**, 332; J. J. DALY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 3799.